

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Barkat, a cold-tolerant variety for the first crop in rice - rice rotations in mid-altitude valleys of Bhutan

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Rice double cropping in the mid-altitude (800-1,500 m) valleys of Bhutan is a recent practice. Cold tolerance at seedling stage is a prerequisite for varieties in the first (Feb-Jul) cropping season when the mean minimum temperature averages 6-8 °C. Seedlings are raised using poly-tunnels that increase the air temperature by 2-4 °C. Despite its cold tolerance and high yield, No. 11 (Takanenishiki), which is currently the only recommended variety for the first cropping season, is extremely difficult to thresh.

The National Variety Release Committee of the Department of Agriculture released in Sep 1992 cold-tolerant variety Barkat—developed in Kashmir, India, from the cross Shinei/China 971—as an alternative to No. 11. Barkat is a semidwarf (90-95 cm) with white, bold grains. It matures earlier (155 d) than No. 11 (160 d) and it can be successfully direct seeded.

In station trials at CARD (1,300 m) during 1988-91, Barkat yielded at par

Performance of Barkat in yield trials.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Barkat	No. 11 (check)
Sequential transplanting trial, 1988	3.1	3.3
Observation nursery, 1989	6.4	6.1
Initial evaluation trial, 1989	5.5	6.1
Advanced evaluation trial, 1990	3.6	4.2
Sequential direct seeding trial, 1991	3.2	3.0
On-farm trials, 1991-92 (12 locations)	4.1	4.2
Mean	4.3	4.5

with No. 11 (see table). Yield was nearly the same for the varieties in on-farm trials at 12 locations conducted over two seasons in 1991-92.

Grain yield, however, is not the primary consideration for farmers in these areas. The major advantage of Barkat over No. 11 is its threshability ease and earlier maturity, which is crucial in a rigid rice - rice rotation.

The rice double-cropped area is expected to increase with the release of Barkat. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Guyana 91, an improved rice variety for Guyana

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Rustic, which is highly susceptible to blast (BI), is grown on more than 66% of Guyana's riceland. A major objective of the National Rice Varietal Improvement Programme has been to develop a BI-resistant variety. IR44624-127-1-2-2-3, an improved IRR line, was critically evaluated during 1990-91 at the NARI Coastal Plain Field Research Unit, in farmers' fields in all of the major rice-growing regions, and in the BI screening nursery (Table 1). The line was released for general cultivation as Guyana 91.

Guyana 91 has high grain yield potential. It is BI resistant and has quality characteristics comparable with those of Rustic (Table 2). It is recommended for cultivation in lowlands and in highly BI-prone areas. ■

Table 1. Performance of Guyana 91.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase over Rustic (%)
	Guyana 91	Rustic	
1990			
On-farm trial	7.2	6.4	12.8
1991			
Replicated yield trial	5.8	5.2	11.8
On-farm yield trial	5.3	5.0	5.2
Mean ^a	6.1	5.5	9.9

^aMean of 5 trials.

Table 2. Varietal characteristics of Guyana 91 and Rustic.

Character	Guyana 91	Rustic
Vegetative vigor	Good	Good
Resistance to lodging	Good	Good
Plant height (cm)	110	85
Senescence	Slow	Fast
Flag leaf	Long, erect	Short, intermediate
Panicle	Long, intermediate	Medium, intermediate
1000-grain weight (g)	26	25
Grain yield potential (t/ha)	6.5	6
Grain type (milled)	Extra-long, slender	Extra-long, slender
Grain length (milled) (mm)	8.0	8.2
Grain width (milled) (mm)	2.2	2.4
Milling recovery (%)	66	65
Brokens (%)	7.81	6.60
Chalkiness (%)	5.35	3.70
Threshing	Easy	Moderate
Grain dormancy	2 wk	None
Growth duration (d)	120	110
Resistance to blast	Resistant	Highly susceptible
Resistance to leaf sheath blight	Resistant	Highly susceptible